

STUDIES ON FRESHWATER FISH PONDS OF WESTERN UTTAR PRADESH

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ABSTRACT: The present communication deals with survey of five fish ponds (two from Muzaffarnagar and three from Saharanpur). During investigation status of fish culture practice with its problems and prospects were studied. Suggestions for problem remedies are also given.

Key words : Fish pond, Muzaffarnagar, Saharanpur.

INTRODUCTION

With the existing sign of over increasing population all over the world, it has become very much essential to tap all the natural resources judiciously for sustainable development and increasing food production, in order to combat the problems of food shortage and malnutrition.

The availability of land for agriculture is decreasing day by day. This has compelled us to diversify our agriculture practice, to cope the demand of food, in face of over increasing population (Thoney and Hargis, 1991).

Fish culture is an oldest branch of animal husbandry which has helped the mankind in procuring him food, in various ways. Thus, fish culture practice has increased world over, during the last twenty years (Conroy and Herman, 1997).

Besides this, fishes usually have better food conversion efficiencies than other live stock because they do not need a substantial skeleton for support and movement like live stock, since they have more or less same density as water. Thus, a higher proportion of their weight is edible and less energy is required for their movement and support. Moreover, since fishes are cold blooded, they do not require energy for the maintenance of higher body temperature like warm blooded animals (Edwards, 1980). Uttar Pradesh is richly endowed with land water resources for development of fisheries. The total area of rivers and canal water in the state is about 7.2 lakh hectares; large and medium size reservoirs are built for the purpose of irrigation and electric power generation, 1.5 lakh hectares of natural lakes, 3.3 lakh hectares of small reservoirs and tanks etc., 1.62 lakh hectares of Gram Sabhas. This all makes 11.65 lakh hectares (Anonymous, 1990). This goodly area of water body in state offers an excellent scope for fish culture practice.

In this context, the proper development of pond for fish culture practice requires serious attention of Scientists. On review of literature, it is evident that very little attention has been paid on this line, on the fish culture practice in India in general, and Western Uttar Pradesh in particular. The only report available on this problem from Western Uttar Pradesh appears to be of Sharma and Kumar (2001).

Thus, with a view to find out the problems encountered by fish farmers in Western U.P., the present investigation was started to assess the social, technological and economical constrains being faced by fish farmers in this region.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A through survey of five different fish ponds (two at district Muzaffarnagar and three at district Saharanpur) were carried out. During investigation I personally visited these ponds from time to time and made various inquiries from the owners of these ponds. Different measurements of water body were made by the method suggested by the Welch (1952).

Important points of inquiry were: Location of pond, Type of pond, Size of pond, Area of pond, Source of water, Personal investigation about the owner, Professional training of owner, Stocking time, Composition of stock, Historical background of pond, Production data and Problems faced by the owner.

OBSERVATION

(A) Baheri Begumpur Pond – 1

- 1) **Location:** Village Baheri Begumpur (14 Km in North, from Muzaffarnagar).
- 2) **Type of Pond:** Man made
- 3) **Size of Pond:** 27.4x25x4 m
- 4) **Source of water:** By tubewell and natural rain

Map 1 : Showing different fish pond of Saharanpur.

water.

5) **Owner:** Mr. Ram Kumar Kashyap, local resident of the village.

6) **Professional training of owner:** Fifteen days training of fish culture, from Department of fisheries, Muzaffarnagar (S.No. 96/38).

7) **Stocking time:** In July every year.

8) **Composition of stock:** *Labeo rohita*, *Catla catla*, *Cirrhina mrigala* and *Cyprinus carpio*.

9) **Historical background of pond:** Pond is about 80 years old. It was unsuitable for fish culture. Owner modified the pond in order to make it suitable for fish culture in 1995, which he took on lease from Gram Sabha for 10 years.

10) **Details of approximate expenditure per year :**

- i) For water - Rs. 15,000
- ii) For labour - Rs. 18,000
- iii) For lime - Rs. 1,600
- iv) For fry - Rs. 80/1000fry.

11) **Problems :**

i) **Administrative / Management problems:**

Land around the pond is the property of resourceful persons of the village. They had claimed on owner to occupy their land. Some persons steal the fishes from the pond at night. Owner is unable to stop theft of fishes. He also failed to get Police protection.

ii) **Technical problems:** Fishes died due to fungal disease of skin during 1998-1999.

iii) **Financial problems:** Amount of Rs. 15,000 was granted to the owner from the bank as loan. This amount is quite meager to manage the fish pond.

iv) **Marketing problems:** Fishermen of this area hold fish markets. They buy the fishes from farmers at quite low price.

(B) **Baheri Begumpur Pond – 2**

1) **Location:** Village Baheri Begumpur (14 Km in North, from Muzaffarnagar).

2) **Type of Pond :** Man made

3) **Size of Pond:** 135x125x2 m

4) **Source of water:** By tubewell and natural rain water.

5) **Owner:** Mr. Sobha Ram Kashyap, local resident of that village.

6) **Professional training of owner:** Traditional occupation of the family, since several generations. No additional training owner has about fish culture.

7) **Stocking time:** In July every year.

8) **Composition of stock:** *Labeo rohita*, *Catla catla* and *Cirrhina mrigala*.

9) **Historical background of pond:** Pond is about 20 years old and under the possession of his own family.

10) Details of approximate expenditure per year:

- i) For water - Rs. 8,000
- ii) For labour - Rs. 4,000
- iii) For fry - Rs. 80/1000fry.

11) **Problems:**

i) **Administrative / Management problems:** Some persons steal the fishes at night from the pond. Owner is unable to stop theft of fishes. Besides this, he also failed in getting Police protection. In the year (1998-1999), some unknown persons introduced fish poison in the pond jealously and all the fishes died during that year.

Table 1 : Showing production data of Baheri Begumpur pond 1.

Year	No. of fry stocked	Investment	Production of fish in kg	Increment
1997-1998	25,000	36,600	2,000	36,000
1998-1999	32,000	37,160	2,800	40,000
1999-2000	47,000	38,360	3,200	42,000

Table 2: Showing production data of Baheri Begumpur pond.2

Year	No. of fry stocked	Investment	Production of fish in kg	Income
1997-1998	1,00,000	20,000	1,200	8,000
1998-1999	1,20,000	21,600	Nil	—————
1999-2000	1,75,000	26,000	1,900	16,000

Table 5: Showing production data of Beedpur pond.

Year	No. of fry stocked	Investment	Production of fish in Kg	Increment
1997-1998	50,000	28,400	2,500	20,000
1998-1999	50,000	28,400	2,600	21,000
1999-2000	70,000	30,000	3,000	28,000

ii) **Technical problems :** Fishes died due to gaseous imbalance of pond water (1999-2000). They were characterized by swollen abdomen.

iii) **Financial problems :** Owner is very poor and needs more money for increasing the fish production from the pond. As many a times, he fails to arrange feed and water for the pond.

iv) **Marketing problems:** Fishermen of this area hold fish markets. They buy the fishes from the farmers at a low cost.

(C) Pilakhni Pond

1) **Location:** Village Pilakhni (8 Km far in West, From Saharanpur)

2) **Type of Pond:** Natural pond.

3) **Size of Pond:** 627x575x3.2 m

4) **Source of water :** By tubewell and natural rain water.

5) **Owner :** Mr. Ram Kumar Kashyap, local resident of the village.

6) **(Professional training of owner :** Fifteen days training of fish culture, from Department of fisheries, Saharanpur.

7) **Stocking time :** In July every year.

Table 3: Showing production data of Pilakhni pond.

Year	No. of fry stocked	Investment	Production of fish in kg	Increment
1997-1998	1,00,000	23,000	3,500	30,000
1998-1999	1,20,000	24,600	4,000	35,000
1999-2000	1,50,000	27,000	3,900	33,000

Table 4 : Showing production data of Shimlana pond.

Year	No. of fry stocked	Investment	Production of fish in Kg	Increment
1997-1998	40,000	7,400	1,500	15,000
1998-1999	60,000	8,800	1,400	12,000
1999-2000	50,000	8,100	700	6,000

8) **Composition of stock:** *Labeo rohita*, *Catla catla*, *Ctenopharyngodon idella* and *Hypophthalmichthys molitrix*.

9) **Historical background of pond:** Pond is about 80 years old and no effort has been made by the farmer to clean the pond.

10) Details of approximate annual expenditure:

i) For water - Rs. 10,000

ii) For Khal - Rs. 3,000

iii) For lime - Rs. 2,000

iv) For fry - Rs. 80/1000fry.

11) Problems:

i) **Administrative / Management problems:** Pond is placed near the owner's home and he does not feel any problem of pond management.

ii) **Technical problems:** Fishes died due to gaseous imbalance of pond water. They were characterized by swollen abdomen. Fishes also died due to a disease called Ichthyophthiriasis (white spot disease), in 1999-2000.

iii) **Financial problems:** Amount of Rs. 20,000 was granted to the owner from the bank as loan, he does not face any financial problem as he is well off.

iv) **Marketing problems:** Fish farmer sells the fishes at Saharanpur fish market and sometimes at Dehradun fish market. He does not feel any problem in marketing the fishes, due to easy availability of transport system.

(D) Shimlana Fish Pond

1) **Location:** Village Shimlana [16Km far, From Deoband (Saharanpur)]

2) **Type of Pond:** Natural pond.

3) **Size of Pond:** 150x100x4 m

4) **Source of water:** By tubewell and natural rain water.

5) **Owner:** Mr. Pappan Kashyap, local resident of the village.

6) **Professional training of owner:** Traditional occupation of family, no technical training has been received.

7) **Stocking time:** In July every year.

8) **Composition of stock:** *Labeo rohita*, *Catla catla* and *Ctenopharyngodon idella*.

9) **Historical background of pond:** Pond is about 50 years old and not cleaned since several years.

10) Details of approximate annual expenditure :

i) For water - Rs. 1,500

ii) For food - Rs. 1,600

iii) For Khal - Rs. 1,500

iv) For fry - Rs. 70/1000fry.

11) Problems:

i) **Administrative / Management problems:** Pond is placed in front of owner's house; he does not feel any problem of pond management.

ii) **Technical problems:** Fishes died (in the year 1999-2000) due to gaseous imbalance of pond water. Some fishes also died (in the year 1999-2000) due to low level of water in the pond during winter season which received no rains.

iii) **Financial problems:** Owner feels shortage of money to invest in the pond in order to increase the fish production.

iv) **Marketing problems:** Fish markets are very far from the pond (about 45 Km, nearest at Saharanpur). Transport expense is very high.

(E) Beedpur Pond

1) **Location:** Village Beedpur (6 Km in North, From Saharanpur).

2) **Type of Pond:** Natural pond.

3) **Size of Pond :** 540x500x3.3 m

4) **Source of water:** By tubewell and natural rain water.

5) **Owner:** Mr. Rishipal, local resident of the village.

6) **Professional training of owner:** Three months training of fish culture, from Department of fisheries, Saharanpur.

7) **Stocking time:** In August every year.

8) **Composition of stock:** *Labeo rohita*, *Catla catla* and *Cirrhina mrigala*.

9) **Historical background of pond:** Pond is about 40 years old.

10) Details of approximate annual expenditure:

i) For water - Rs. 10,000

ii) For servant - Rs. 14,400

iii) For fry - Rs. 80/1000fry.

11) Problems:

i) **Administrative / Management problems:** Some persons steal the fishes from the pond so the farmer has kept a servant for pond care (1200/month).

ii) **Technical problems:** In rains, fishes come out from the pond due to over flow of water of the pond. The growth of some fishes was inhibited due to Dropsy (liver disease).

iii) **Financial problems:** Owner needs money for managing the pond, he had applied in bank for loan, but loan was not granted.

iv) **Marketing problems:** Fishermen hold the fish markets. They buy the fishes from the farmers at a low cost.

DISCUSSION

During investigation I found that despite of variety of problems, per unit area production from the aquatic body is about 3-5 times higher than land. If it is taken scientifically it will be certainly going to reward good dependures to farmers of small land holdings with less risk.

On the basis of observation I recommends following measures to be taken in order to overcome the problems of fish farmers of this region and increase the fish production —

1) Farmers should be trained thoroughly by State Fisheries Departments/Fish Farmers Development Agencies (FFDAs)/National Council of Applied Economic Research (NCAER). This training program should be concentrated upon —

i) Making chemical and physical analysis of soil and water and its treatment to make it hospitable for stocking fishes.

ii) Explaining stocking density to farmers, so that they should not stock fishes more than carrying capacity of the pond.

iii) Training the farmers, on how to select the proper fishes for stocking so that each and every column of water must be utilized aptly.

iv) Training must also be given to raise their own broods for the seeds or State Fisheries Departments should take care of this aspect.

v) Training them for the disease contingencies which arise in the pond.

2) Local funding agencies like Nationalized Banks / NABARD / FFDA's / NCAER to raise some funds for the farmers, so that they can perform proper culture practice.

3) Local administration must be taken into confidence to solve the problems of poaching, poisoning and threat to the poor and small fish farmers.

4) In order to solve the marketing problems, State Fisheries Departments together with other State Departments should take care of their products like other agricultural products like sugarcane, paddy, wheat, cotton etc.

5) Universities and State Fisheries Departments are advised to organise training programs / Seminars / Workshops, so that farmers should know what they have to do and when.

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